

Performance assessment of Seawater, Wet and Dry cooling in a 50MW Parabolic Trough Collectors CSP plant in Kuwait

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Abstract

Kuwait is a country with great potential for Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) due to its high solar resource. The current work analyzes the potential of application of CSP technology in the country and its particularities. Specifically, the current work examines a CSP Plant with Parabolic Trough Collector (PTC) technology and how this technology is affected in its performance depending on the location (inland or coastal) and the refrigeration system (wet, dry or seawater cooled). The modeling methodology is based on a two-step approach: first, the Rankine steam power cycle is modelled in detail in a state-of-the-art steady-state simulation environment, obtaining the performance of the power cycle for each cooling technology; second, the power cycle performance maps are integrated into a detailed transient system level simulation model of the complete CSP plant in order to perform annual yield simulations for the different representative locations of the Climate of Kuwait. These results provide valuable information on both the potential of this technology for its more immediate application such as electricity generation and other future applications such as the desalination of seawater where the location must necessarily be coastal.

Keywords: Concentrated Solar Power; Parabolic Trough Collectors; Solar Plant performance; Solar Plant transient modelling; Rankine Cycle simulation; Cooling systems

1. Introduction

Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) or solar thermal electricity (STE) represents a very promising renewable technology, particularly due to the very relevant feature of cheap thermal energy storage, guaranteeing dispatchability. Along the last decade, CSP Plants for electricity production at utility scale have widely proven its economic feasibility and are currently being deployed worldwide. Their unique characteristic of being dispatchable at competitive cost outstands among other renewable sources. Therefore, CSP plants are essential to integrate large shares of renewables into the grid, providing firm renewable capacity. Among the main CSP technologies, the Power Tower technology represents a very promising one due to its potential for both increased efficiency and cost reduction. Nonetheless, the parabolic trough collector (PTC) technology (despite a lower performance when compared to Tower) represents the highest level of reliability and is the most frequent technological option among the past, current and future planned total set of CSP Plants [1].

42 The increase in CSP worldwide installed capacity, especially in the last decade, can be considered as
43 a proof of CSP competitiveness in energy markets [2]. Nonetheless there still exists the need to
44 achieve technological improvements and breakthroughs that may allow a step ahead for both cost
45 reductions and also new plant concepts for hybridization and integration with thermal processes.
46 In accordance with this last development pathway (new plant concepts), thermal desalination
47 processes integration with CSP is a specific work line. In that latter context, countries in deserted
48 areas suffer lack of water and specifically the current research work covers different Kuwait sites
49 climates.

50 Kuwait country is placed at the Arabian Peninsula, whose countries are also known as the Gulf Cost
51 Council (GCC). The average annual rain level in these countries is from 5 to 45 mm/y whilst in the
52 driest European countries (mainly those in the Mediterranean EU) it ranges from 200 to 400
53 mm/year. Nowadays, there exists a strong link between energy and water. In a recent report,
54 IRENA [3] states that worldwide 15% of global fresh water use is for energy production (including
55 oil extraction) and 55% of water utilities' operating budget is due to energy costs.

56 The GCC area is also wealthy in solar radiation, which can be used for desalination, integrated with
57 CSP Plants. The aim of this latter option is to take advantage of the physical principles behind CSP
58 technologies to efficiently couple the thermal cycle of the CSP plant to a water desalination system
59 achieving a desalination plant whose energy is mostly or completely supplied by renewable energy
60 [4,5]. The relatively large land area available in these countries enables to use the solar power to
61 produce enough water to cope the water needs.

62 A desalination plant will almost certainly be located near the coast, so a plant integrating both CSP
63 + desalination opens an additional option for the Thermal cycle cooling (besides traditional
64 wet/dry cooling against ambient air) based in direct use of seawater, which is less sensitive to
65 ambient temperature and benefits of the outstanding properties of liquid water for heat transfer
66 and transport as cooling medium. The potential of such near coastal CSP plants for being cooled
67 with seawater, is scarcely studied in the existing CSP literature, and will be explored at a costal site
68 alongside the classic wet/dry comparison for an inland site at Kuwait. The research outcomes will
69 provide information for developing at arid and coastal sites of the country of Kuwait, both new PTC
70 plants and next-gen CSP + desalination ones.

71 **2. Methodology**

72 The general methodology used in the present work is summarized in the following points:

73 1. Design of specific CSP plant schemes for the following list of power cycle cooling method

- 74 a. Dry cooling
- 75 b. Wet cooling
- 76 c. Seawater cooling

77 First of all, establish a baseline case of a CSP Plant accordingly to specifications of the existing
78 operational 50MWe Dry-Cooled Shagaya CSP Plant at Kuwait [6]. Then integrate the different
79 Power Block Cooling systems, preserving the baseline case specifications and dimensions for the
80 rest of the Plant. Design the particular sub-scheme for each cooling system.

81 2. Comprehensive Power Block modelling for the 3 options using specific software.

82 Start determining the three-power block (steam generator, turbine, steam bleedings, cooling
83 system) schemes from state-of-the-art technology used in CSP Plants. Afterwards do the modelling
84 of each Power Block solution using state-of-the-art software (IPSEpro [7]) for power cycle
85 simulation. Then determine each Power Block solution performance by simulation for different
86 operational and ambient conditions. Finally, Generate lookup tables for the main power block
87 performance parameters for different operational and ambient conditions

- 88 3. Create an overall plant transient model and parametrization for the particular characteristics of
89 CSP Plant placed at Kuwait
- 90 Select suitable CSP Plant Modelling software (Dymola™ [8]) and choose an appropriate library
91 (CENER in-house Open Modelica-based) of Concentrated Solar Power and thermal systems. Then
92 perform transient modelling of the CSP Plant and Power Block schemes determined in points 1 and
93 2. Integrate a Partial Model for the power block subsystem using an approach based in lookup
94 tables. Finally complete the process with the parametrization of each main component in the Plant
95 Overall Model.
- 96 4. Climate data selection for a representative set of arid and seaside regions in Kuwait.
- 97 Determine the representative number of sites to be studied. Select appropriate models for
98 predictions, using multi-year database and high time and spatial resolution obtained from satellite
99 data. Apply regional adaptation (taking into account specific factors like aerosols) to the radiation
100 models, in order to provide an accurate radiation prediction. Last step is generating a Typical
101 Meteorological Year (TMY) for each site.
- 102 5. Simulation for the different climates and Plant schemes for best performance.
- 103 a. Dry / Wet Cooling at Inland site
104 b. Dry / Wet / Seawater at Coastal site
- 105 Using the selected software, simulate the models generated in point 3 and using the climate data
106 from point 4. Ensure a systematic collect of each plant output performance data for further analysis.
- 107 6. Selection of the best schemes and assessment of plant performance.
- 108 Critically revise the performance data obtained from point 5 to determine whether refining or
109 model debugging is needed. Apply data treatment to obtain key performance parameters and merit
110 figures of each CSP Plant. Final step is assessing each plant performance parameter and outputs.
- 111 7. Analysis of the relevant parameters and the improvement reached for the best plant schemes
- 112 Analyze Plant performances. Carry out a comparison among all sites and cooling options. Derive
113 and create the relevant conclusions from the results. To conclude, analyze the interest and
114 feasibility of at least one future work line.

115 3. Simulation Model

116 A general CSP plant transient simulation model has been developed. That model has been used to
117 calculate the energy yield of different schemes integrating the different options for the Rankine
118 power block. A Parabolic Trough CSP plant scheme similar to the state-of-the-art commercial
119 systems has been chosen as a design basis. The cooling system, as has been explained, has three
120 qualitative different solutions. A schematic of the Plant layout with all relevant components is
121 provided in the Fig. 1.

122 The CSP system model implementation has been performed using OpenModelica language and
123 applying a commercial simulation tool, integrating specific partial models for each subsystem
124 which are depicted later. Thanks to the philosophy of OpenModelica, a flexible object-oriented
125 approach, the different plant models are built upon reusable component models, reducing the
126 implementation effort. The software provides specific components for data readers, controls,
127 integrators and statistics.

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Fig. 1 PTC 2-tank indirect CSP Plant scheme with a generic cooling system

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The basic operation of the plant is as follows: The HTF is heated up in the solar field, stored in the TES, or directly pumped through the steam generator producing steam for the power block, which produces electricity in a conventional water-steam cycle. The heat can be stored being transferred to the TES system, via a heat exchanger. The sensible heat is stored in molten salt (nitrate solar salt), which is pumped from the cold to the hot tank. The flow direction is reversed for discharge mode. The Plant has been parametrized in accordance to its main physical and control components. The main plant characteristics are listed in the Table 1, which are obtained from the operational CSP Plant Shagaya in Kuwait [6]

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Table 1. Main Plant parameters

Characteristic	Description
CSP Technology	Parabolic Trough
HTF type	Synthetic Thermal Oil
HTF nominal temperatures	393°C / 295°C
Thermal Storage	2 Tank, Indirect, Solar Salt
Plant Nominal Electric Power	50MWe
Mirrors total Aperture area	673620 m ²
Number of collector loops	206
Aperture/Length/number of Solar Collector Assemblies	5.77 m / 148.6 m / 48
Power Block	Subcritical regenerative Steam Rankine
Solar Field Layout	North - South
Nominal Thermal Storage capacity	1200 MWhth (>9h)
Solar Multiple at design point (Solar position on June 21, DNI=900/m ²)	2.78

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3.1. Solar Field Model

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A detailed transient numerical model of a parabolic trough collector is needed to perform detailed simulations of the entire power plant under transient operating conditions. It is thus possible to analyze the start-up and shut-down behavior as well as the plant's transient response to disturbances throughout the day, caused by variations in incident solar direct normal irradiation.

144 Basically, the model is based on the idea a 1-D energy balance similar to which was initially
 145 proposed by Forristall [9] discretizing the solar collector loop into a certain number of control
 146 volumes. To correctly reproduce the dominant dynamics and the steady-state behavior, a certain
 147 minimum number of control volumes per loop are required. According to Zaversky [10], a
 148 discretization level of 3 control volumes per solar collector of about 50 m length is considered to be
 149 accurate enough for transient performance simulations. The model is built on top of past and
 150 current literature review and furthermore on a well-structured and flexible modeling approach as
 151 proposed by the Modelica Standard Library (version 3.2.3). The one-dimensional fluid flow & heat
 152 transfer model of the solar absorber, And a simplified scheme of a cross section of the absorber, are
 153 represented in the Fig. 2.

154 The discretization of the pipe into a number of finite control volumes is done according to the finite
 155 volume method, solving the basic equations for mass and energy conservation for each of them. The
 156 momentum balance is reduced to its steady-state formulation, by neglecting differences in velocity
 157 and the influence of the gravitational force. Hence, the HTF flow within the absorber tube is
 158 discretized using control volumes of equal size. This approach corresponds to that already
 159 proposed by several authors [9, 12, 13], and can be considered as the standard approach. The solar
 160 heat input due to absorption of the concentrated solar radiation in the parabolic mirrors, is
 161 implemented coupling each discrete absorber tube section with one solar heat input model element
 162 that basically applies the standard PTC modeling approach [14-16] , taking into account cosine
 163 effect loss, shading loss, optical efficiency, and an empirical correlation for the incidence angle
 164 modifier (IAM).

(a)

(b)
 Fig. 2 Block diagram (a) and simplified schematics (b) of the object-oriented parabolic trough collector model scheme showing the energy balance. This model has been validated against experimental data [10,11]

In order to also account for the solar absorption within the glass envelope, which is determined by the solar absorptance of the glass, the solar heat input model is split into two parallel parts, i.e. one for the solar absorptance at the receiver tube, and one for the solar absorptance at the glass envelope (see Fig. 2), each applying the corresponding optical efficiency. The transient heat conduction equations of the glass envelope have been modified by adding a simple source term that acts at the central temperature, specifically adapting conduction model for the glass envelope.

The other design aspect for to the definition of the collector model is the solar field's pressure drop, since the pumping power required for circulating the heat transfer fluid is usually around 5% of the plant's gross output. The change in pressure ΔP in each segment is calculated with an equation to calculate pressure loss in a horizontal pipe with fully developed turbulent flow [17], being the Darcy friction factor calculated for turbulent pipe flow with the Colebrook equation. These equations are implemented in the model for each segment of the computational domain.

3.2. Thermal Storage

The model is based in an active indirect two-tank system, using molten salts as storage medium, and Thermal Oil as HTF as it is currently applied at commercial power plants. The molten salt inventory is modeled as ideally mixed, having one representative temperature. Thus, the same approach has been applied to the gas atmosphere above the molten salt level as well. The heat loss to the ambient is modeled in transient mode, by taking the thermal inertia of the tank's steel container as well as that of the insulation material into account. The radiative heat transfer between the surface of the molten salt and the non-wetted parts of the tank's steel jacket is considered assuming an ideal cylindrical geometry. The convective heat transfer coefficients at the wetted inner surfaces of the tank's steel jacket are assumed to be constant. The heat transfer at the tank's outer surfaces is split into the convective and the radiative part. The incident solar radiation and its absorption are also considered, to allow a reasonable approximation of the influence of

193 altering environmental boundary conditions. These assumptions lead to an overall transient model
194 structure shown in the Fig. 3.

195 3.3. Power Block

196 In order to obtain an accurate calculation of the power block behaviour and the electric output
197 under the different conditions and cooling options, three detailed power block models
198 implementing each solution have been developed. These models are built using IPSEpro software
199 [7], implementing partial models for each characteristic component of the cycle and solving
200 coupled the mass and energy balance equations of each component of the power block. It has been
201 used to model both partial load and design point conditions. A typical power block configuration
202 commonly used in 50MWe CSP PTC Plants. The characteristic common parameters of the Rankine
203 cycle are shown in the Table 2.

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Parameter	Value
Nominal live steam temperature	380 °C
Nominal live steam pressure	100 bar
Blowdown mass flow fraction	1.1 %
Pressure drop at steam generator	4 bar
Gland steam and leakages mass flow fraction	0.8 %
Electrical and mechanical generator efficiency	0.98
Electrical and mechanical motor efficiency	0.98
Preheaters Terminal Temperature Difference (TTC)	5 °C
Preheaters Drain Cooler Approach (DCA)	5 °C

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206 The Steam Generator System (SGS) comprises the following heat exchangers: economizer,
207 evaporator, superheater, and reheater. The power block is equipped with a regenerative feed-water
208 system (five surface preheaters and a deaerator). The heat exchanger models are implemented
209 according to the logarithmic mean temperature difference method [18]. The product between the
210 overall heat transfer coefficient and the heat transfer area (UA) is calculated at design conditions,
211 then each value for this parameter is fixed, being a valid assumption due to the low variation of the
212 mass flow with the Thermal Oil inlet temperature. The condensing options are shown in the Table
213 3.

214 The condensing pressures for Dry, Wet and Seawater cooling are obtained from real operating
215 power plants specifications. It is noteworthy that Wet Cooling systems exhibits, at the design point,
216 a higher pressure (0.063 bar > 0.055 bar) than Seawater Cooling ones, in spite of a condensing
217 medium lower inlet temperature (22°C<25°C). This pressure is always a compromising decision for
218 the power cycle designer, considering the lower performance when off-design point operation and
219 its penalty. A key aspect is the expected temperature variation of the cooling fluid along a year, and
220 its compatibility with the condensing pressure, condenser heat exchange surface and pumping
221 systems. Lower temperature oscillations are expected from sea water, compared to an evaporative
222 cooling tower placed at Kuwait climate. So the worst expected operation conditions (see Table 5)
223 could allow to keep such low condensing pressure values (0.055 bar) for the seawater cooling
224 option, with an appropriate dimensioning of the steam-water condenser for this extreme
225 operational condition.

Table 3. Parameters of each Power Block cooling option			
	Dry Cooling	Wet Cooling	Seawater cooled
Condenser type	forced-draft direct air-cooled	water-cooled	water-cooled
Condensing pressure at nominal point	0.17 bar	0.063 bar (obtained from CENER's private data of operational CSP PTC Plants)	0.055 bar [25]
Condensing medium Mass flow and inlet/outlet at nominal conditions	Air 1bar, 25°C 3112kg/s 25/53.6°C	Water 22°C 2231kg/s 22/30.8°C	Water 25°C 2343kg/s 25/32.8°C
Other		Wet cooling tower with N=2.5 (N=cycles of concentration in the evaporative circuit of the cooling water)	

226 The water/steam properties are implemented according to the IAPWS [19]. The isentropic
 227 efficiency of each turbine stage is a function of its relative inlet mass flow and its nominal gross
 228 power. For part-load, correction factors have been obtained from ThermoSysPro library [20]
 229 developed by EDF and released under open source license. The Fig. 4 (a) shows the cycle
 230 configuration diagram as well as the pressure, temperature, enthalpy, and mass flow values in the
 231 different streams at the design point for the wet-cooling option. The reference crosses show the
 232 variables this way: Pressure in bar (bottom left), mass flow in kg/s (top left), specific enthalpy in
 233 kJ/kg (top right) and temperature in degrees Celsius (bottom right). In the Fig. 4b there is a
 234 simplified schematic of the power block showing the main points, with numbered points
 235 corresponding to the equivalent points in the cycle diagram on Fig.4a.

236 3.4. Cooling systems partial models

237 The state of the art for heat rejection in thermal power plants is based in evaporative wet cooling
 238 towers. That solution, however, needs considerable amounts of make-up water. At typical CSP sites,
 239 water is a scarce and thus cannot always be used for the cooling of the power plant. The water
 240 needed for cleaning the solar field mirrors nearly deplete the water resources at certain locations
 241 and is the main constraint to design the cooling technology. The three proposed cooling systems are
 242 described more in detail in the following paragraphs.

243 a) Dry Cooling

244 Because of water scarcity, dry air-cooled condensers are a common solution for concentrated solar
 245 power applications. Due to the relatively high ambient air temperatures, the condensing pressure
 246 has to be increased compared to wet cooled plants, which reduces the Rankine cycle's efficiency.
 247 Another shortcoming is the limited convective heat transfer coefficient on the air side of the
 248 condenser. Because of that, the heat exchange area has to be very large in order to keep the fan
 249 power and thus the condenser's parasitic power consumption at an acceptable level. The approach
 250 for modelling is based in the implemented according to the logarithmic mean temperature
 251 difference method [18], fixing the parameters in accordance to calculations compliant to what is
 252 exposed in [23].

■ Modelica heat connector (connecting equations: temperatures are set equal, heat flows sum up to zero)

(a)

(b)

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Fig. 3 Block diagram (a) and simplified schematics (b) of the numerical model of the TES subsystem and the energy balance. The model has been validated against experimental data [21,22].

(a)

(b)

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Fig. 4 Wet cooling Power Block schematic diagram showing the main points (b), and simulated (IpsEPRO software) operational conditions for this scheme at the design point (a)

258 b) Wet cooling

259 Wet cooling tower (also called “Evaporative cooling”) is the most common cycle cooling technology
260 in thermal power plants. Waste heat is dissipated to air via evaporation of secondary flow cooling
261 water, separate from the water/steam stream of the cycle. High ambient relative humidity also
262 might limit the performance of these systems, constraining the air ability to evaporate water by
263 adiabatic humidification. Wet cooling systems perform better than dry cooled systems in areas with
264 high ambient temperatures and low ambient humidity.

265 Fig. 5 Wet cooling tower condensing system [23] for a steam Rankine cycle and main operating parameters
266 (b)

267 Despite current state of art in numerical models [24], mainly Merkel and Poppe models for wet
268 cooling towers modelling, that partial model has been implemented based in a performance map
269 for a range within the expected operating conditions, based in the following independent variables:
270 Ambient dry and wet bulb temperature, Inlet water Mass Flow, Inlet water temperature, Approach
271 and Range, in accordance with Fig.5b. The machine is selected for the design point and the off
272 design performance parameters are provided by n-dimensional interpolation of the data matrix.
273 The dependent variables are parasitic power and air mass flow. The information for building the
274 performance map is an outcome of the collaboration work with a reference manufacturer of
275 industrial cooling systems, which has several wet cooling systems operational at CSP PTC Plants in
276 Spain.

277 A key parameter to quantify the water consumption in the tower is referred in the Table 3 as N,
278 which is the Cycles of concentration in the cooling tower circulating flow. This value represents the
279 water renewal rate (besides the water consumption due to evaporation) needed to prevent high
280 concentrations of corroding compounds in the cooling water circuits.

281 c) Seawater cooling

282 The location of a thermal power cycle near a big mass of water (mighty rivers, reservoirs, sea)
283 enables the direct use of these water resources for condensing the thermal cycle. Surface water
284 masses are less sensitive to ambient temperature and so the low parasitic power required for
285 pumping the cooling medium are the main advantages of this option. As exposed in the
286 introductory part, a proposal for renewable desalination concepts are CSP Plants located near the
287 sea, integrated with thermal desalination systems taking advantage of the thermal cycle heat
288 rejection, underpinning the proposed work approach. The distance to the sea is a critical design
289 point. The Typical Solar Field of a CSP PTC 50MWel Plant, with 9h of Storage, covers around 2km²
290 of land area (view Fig. 6 a, b). Even placing the power island of the plant in the side or corner closer
291 to the sea, for practical considerations a set of three lengths of piping distance to the sea of a
292 minimum of 1km, plus 5km and 10km has been considered. The basic assumptions for calculating
293 the pumping power are: Water average velocity of 2.8 m/s at nominal flow (Table 3) and a pumping

294 efficiency of 0.7, for an insulated horizontal pipe exposed to ambient. As shown in the Table 4, the
295 condensing pressure is in accordance to values from real power plants in the seaside of Kuwait [25,
296 26].

297 Fig. 6 Termosol CSP Plant CSP, Spain, 50MWe, 9h of TES, (b) Delingha 50MW Thermal Oil PTC project,
298 China, 50MWe, 9h of TES. Source: <https://www.google.com/maps>

299 3.5. Control and operational assumptions

300 The whole plant model is completed with a control module, able to represent the routinely
301 operation of the plant. This involves dynamically controlling the following main loops:

- 302 ○ Solar field focusing
- 303 ○ Solar field HTF mass flow for collecting solar energy
- 304 ○ TES Molten Salts storage charge
- 305 ○ TES Molten Salts storage discharge (which in turns is controlling the power cycle
306 operation)

307 The Power block is driven at its nominal thermal load with an On-Off control with hysteresis based
308 on a minimum thermal storage fill factor to stop operation and a dead band to start the power cycle.

309 Aspects related to durability and accelerated aging of the Plant components (mirrors and their
310 influence on the performance) have been neglected in this study.

311 4. Simulation sites and Meteorological Data

312 In the scope of a previous specific research for characterizing the climate in the GCC region and
313 specifically at Kuwait, five sites have been object of studies and generation of a Typical
314 Meteorological Years (TMY) for each one. The selected sites are representative of the coastal solar
315 resource of Kuwait (from North to South). In addition, an inland location, away from the coast
316 (coincident with the CSP Plant of Shagaya), has been selected to complement this knowledge and
317 also to compare with existing solar previous resource assessments. A 16-years database (from
318 February 2004 to January 2016) at 15-min time resolution and ~5 km spatial resolution, generated
319 from Meteosat Second Generation satellite through the Heliosat method, is used as baseline
320 knowledge for the solar resource assessment.

321 For the current work, the raw modeled solar radiation database, provided by CAMS-Rad, is
322 generated by means of the Heliosat-4 methodology [27] applied to Meteosat Second Generation
323 satellite. This database has been enhanced at the region through adaptation techniques developed
324 in the framework of the Task 16 IEA-PVPS [28, 29]. Meteorological parameters used in this study
325 have been extracted from the Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications
326 Version 2, MERRA-2, hosted by NASA and generated by the Goddard Space Flight Center [31]. The
327 procedure for generating the TMYs at the selected sites from these 16-year solar and

328 meteorological databases has been based on the UNE 206011:2014 [30, 32, 33]. The geographic
 329 distribution map of the sites is shown in Fig. 7.

330 The Kuwait South site has been selected among coastal sites because of its higher annual DNI,
 331 despite being very similar among them. The coastal sites chosen are the ones with the highest and
 332 the lowest DNI among the sites characterized. The summary of the solar resource and average
 333 temperature for each site is provided in the Table 4.

334

335 Fig. 7 Analyzed sites with available solar resource and meteorological TMY (in yellow) and the seawater
 336 data source (in light blue)

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Table 4. Monthly solar DNI values (kWh/m ²) for TMY and annual average temperature (Tavg, in green, degrees Celsius) at the analyzed sites.														
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Year	Tavg
Coast Kuwait Bay	107	103	137	134	153	212	202	203	203	164	115	112	1846	26.58
Coast North	114	111	156	134	162	212	203	206	205	173	124	112	1911	25.98
Coast Middle North	105	114	155	141	157	211	203	207	204	170	118	105	1891	26.15
Coast Middle South	114	110	157	134	163	212	203	206	205	173	124	112	1913	26.29
Coast South	111	109	153	132	169	214	204	206	210	175	127	115	1924	26.57
Inland Shagaya	92	120	166	144	170	215	212	215	205	177	118	95	1929	25.30

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339 The seawater surface temperature data were acquired from [34,35] and an average of the last 10
 340 years has been calculated for the available data close to the city of Al Manqaf, the closest site
 341 available, shown in the Table 5. Given the limited dimension of the country of Kuwait, and the
 342 centered geographical position of this site along the coast, it can considered representative for all
 343 the country coastal sites for analyzing the seawater potential as cooling medium.

Table 5. Monthly Sea water surface temperature (°C)													
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Year
Al Manqaf	16.4	16.0	18.4	22.1	26.6	29.8	31.6	32.8	32.1	29.1	24.3	19.4	24.9

5. Simulation Results and Analysis

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345 After simulating the proposed power block schemes at the different sites, information of the main
 346 plant operational and performance parameters and variables is available. Apart from gross,
 347 parasitic and net energy, it is and shown for each plant scheme the total incident DNI for the
 348 aperture area of the plant, the used DNI (the difference respect to the total incident DNI is the
 349 energy loss when defocusing of the optical system), and the absorber incident radiation (result of
 350 the modelling represented in Fig. 2 which enables to calculate the overall optical efficiency). It is
 351 also provided information of the ambient temperatures, for all the year and other one only while
 352 power block operates.

353 Specific water consumption for each case is also provided. It is noteworthy to point out that dry
 354 cooling water consumption, in spite of no having consumption in the air cooler, is due to cycle
 355 leakages and evaporator blowdown for cycle water purification. Wet cooling water consumption
 356 includes the total make up water required, taking into account also the same leakages and
 357 blowdown, and also the fraction of makeup water in accordance to the cycles of concentration
 358 referred in Table 3. The results corresponding to dry and wet cooling schemes, for the three
 359 simulated sites are shown in Table 6.

360 All the simulated schemes at the Coastal south site overtake the performance of the baseline case
 361 (Shagaya Dry cooled). The coastal Kuwait Bay site, the most likely to be worst site in accordance to
 362 Table 4, yields a lower performance than the baseline case for the dry cooling scheme. For each site,
 363 wet cooling technology provide a net DNI-to-Electric efficiency increase within the 9.29%-10.81%
 364 (relative) interval, compared to the more simple dry cooling technology. The best result among all
 365 sites and schemes is the wet cooled-based coastal site, whose net DNI-to-Electric efficiency
 366 increases over baseline case a 10.81%.

367 For both dry cooling and wet cooling schemes, it is obtained a better performance for the Coastal
 368 south site compared to the baseline Inland case. A preliminary estimation might predict a lower
 369 ambient temperature due to sea temperance influence in local climate, but the annual average
 370 temperature is higher at the coastal that at the inland site. The explanation is that colder night
 371 temperatures (due radiative heat loss to the sky) lower the annual average especially at deserted
 372 sites. When including in the models a weighted average ambient temperature linked to power block
 373 operation, the results correlate as expected to ambient temperature. Then, the weighted averaged
 374 ambient temperatures (whilst the power block operates) are lower at coastal sites for all cases.

375 For the seawater cooled option, for different piping lengths, the obtained results are shown in Table
 376 7. All Seawater-cooled CSP Plants schemes at Coastal south site, for the current study water velocity
 377 assumptions, have a clear improvement over baseline case. For 5 km long piping, the performance
 378 is slightly higher than wet cooling Plants at the same conditions, (14.35 % Net DNI-to-Electric
 379 efficiency). For 10km piping length performance fall below the one provided by a wet cooling Plant,
 380 but still keeps remarkably higher than a dry cooled plant.

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Table 6. Performance parameters for each scheme at simulated sites (*from real data of operational CSP Plants)						
	Inland Dry (baseline)	Coastal South Dry	Coastal Kuwait Bay Dry	Inland Wet	Coastal South Wet	Coastal Kuwait Bay Wet
Site DNI (kWh/m ² -year)	1929	1924	1846	1929	1924	1846
Total incident DNI (GWh)	1370.7	1367.7	1313.5	1370.6	1367.8	1313.5
Used DNI (GWh)	1222.1	1236.9	1186.3	1181.7	1199.2	1153.4
Dumped solar energy (GWh)	148,7	130,9	127,2	189,0	168,6	160,1
Absorber Incident Radiation (GWh)	819.1	820.7	786.2	789.5	793.1	762.0
Gross Energy (GWhe)	203.9	206.8	196.5	221.7	221.1	212.5
Total parasitic Energy (GWhe)	26.6	23.7	26.8	27.5	25.0	26.8
Total Net Energy (GWhe)	177.3	183.1	169.7	194.1	196.1	185.7
Capacity Factor	0.466	0.472	0.449	0.506	0.505	0.49
Solar Field Efficiency	0.598	0.600	0.599	0.576	0.580	0.580
Total time when the storage system is fully charged (h)	584	537	481	698	647	569
Net DNI-to-Electric efficiency	12.94%	13.39%	12.92%	14.16%	14.33%	14.14%
Gross Energy Increase (%)	0%	1.41%	-3.62%	8.73%	8.42%	4.21%
Net Energy Increase (%)	0%	3.26%	-4.28%	9.49%	10.57%	4.73%
Net DNI-to-Electric efficiency Increase over baseline case (%)	0%	3.48%	-0.11%	9.50%	10.81%	9.29%
Specific Water consumption in power block (m ³ /GWhe)	300*	300*	300*	3101	3170	3235
Ambient temperature annual average (°C)	25.3	26.6	26.6	25.3	26.6	26.6
Ambient temperature annual average whilst Power Block Operation (°C)	32.0	31.4	32.2	31.6	31.1	31.9

384

385 Extrapolation suggests that for the same assumptions, a total pipe length of around 20-25 km
386 would have a performance similar to that of a dry-cooled plant placed in the same climate. To
387 determine accurately the system performance for such a long piping would require specific
388 modelling and other simulation assumptions (exposition to weather and solar radiation for outdoor
389 or transient cooling to ground if buried).

390 The average daily seawater needs for cycle cooling, calculated by integration in the simulations, is
391 over 106,000m³/day. This number provides basic information for integrating such a CSP Plant with
392 facilities which involve pumping seawater (i.e, desalination plants). A bar plot of the net efficiency
393 for all simulated schemes and sites is shown in the Fig. 8.

394 The best result among all sites and schemes is the seawater cooled-based coastal site, whose net
395 DNI-to-Electric efficiency remarkably increases over baseline case (+12.98% relative) for a piping
396 length of 1 km or less.

397

398

Table 7. Performance parameters for seawater cooled with different piping lengths			
	Coastal South Seawater 1km	Coastal South Seawater 5km	Coastal South Seawater 10km
Site DNI (kWh/m ² -year)	1924		
Total incident DNI (GWh)	1367.7		
Used DNI (GWh)	1205.4		
Absorber Incident Radiation (GWh)	797.5		
Gross Energy (GWh)	223.7		
Seawater Pumping parasitic Energy (GWh)	1.6	5.1	8.7
Total parasitic Energy (GWh)	23.9	27.4	30.9
Total Net Energy (GWh)	199.9	196.3	192.8
Solar Field Efficiency	0.583		
Capacity Factor	0.511		
Daily average water volume needs for cycle condensing (m ³)	106300		
Net DNI-to-Electric efficiency	14.61%	14.35%	14.10%
Gross Energy Increase (%)	9.75%	9.71%	9.75%
Net Energy Increase (%)	12.74%	10.72%	8.75%
Net DNI-to-Electric efficiency Increase over baseline case	12.98%	10.96%	8.99%

400

401

Fig. 8 Net DNI-to-Electric Performance of all simulated cooling options and sites

402 6. Conclusions

403 Main final conclusions derived from this study can be summarized as follows:

- 404 • A comprehensive comparative assessment has been performed for a representative set of
405 climates of Kuwait providing a performance evaluation for the CSP potential alongside the
406 country.
- 407 • A thorough and detailed transient modeling of a CSP Plant has been developed to assess
408 the performance of different feasible cooling systems in different CSP plant schemes, which
409 is one of the most important design parameters of a CSP plant.
- 410 • The Climate characterization methodology approach followed in this study at several
411 locations of Kuwait, a country of small size and limited orography, allows deducting, under
412 the rest of current work assumptions, that a coastal site should not necessarily be rejected
413 as a candidate for a CSP Plant location against and inland site.
- 414 • For this work assumptions, a good Kuwait coastal site, in spite of expected near-the-sea
415 atmospheric attenuation penalty (-0.3% in the Coastal South site), can provide a better
416 performance (up to +3.48% relative Net DNI-to-Electric efficiency) when compared to
417 baseline Inland case. Night operation strategies could revert that conclusion in favor of
418 inland deserted sites
- 419 • Seawater cooled CSP Plants at Coastal Regions can reach a remarkable increase in net
420 efficiency (up to 12.98% relative in this study) over dry cooled baseline case, for moderate
421 piping lengths (1km or less). They also performed better than wet cooled plants for pipe
422 lengths up to around 5km, for this work assumptions
- 423 • Renewable Desalination and CSP integration is a feasible solution for a Coastal site, and
424 that take advantages of several synergies (seawater cooling, common pumping water from
425 the sea) and having no efficiency penalty for CSP Plant if a good coastal site is chosen.
- 426 • A future work that deserves to be explored is the current technical and economic
427 framework of CSP and renewable desalination. It should address at least the following two
428 points in its scope:
 - 429 ○ Integration of a seawater cooled CSP Plant with a desalination facility exploring all
430 the synergies.
 - 431 ○ Perform a techno economic assessment for 100% renewable water production
432 from solar desalination processes and comparison to other 100% renewable
433 desalination technologies, for an up-to-date economic and energy framework.

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